

Litter quality visual assessment in broiler sheds

Context and objective

Maintaining high-quality litter (meaning dry and friable) is a primary objective in the management of poultry houses, as poor-quality litter could have significant consequences on the health and welfare of birds. A good litter quality provides insulation and cushioning for the birds from the floor, contributing to their comfort by keeping them dry (Collett, 2012). A dry and friable litter is also essential for the birds' welfare, enabling the expression of natural behaviours such as scratching, foraging or dust bathing (Welfare Quality®, 2009). Conversely, soiled litter can have negative consequences on birds' health and welfare: increasing incidence of footpad dermatitis in poultry (Shepherd and Fairchild, 2010; Shepherd et al., 2017); impairing the realisation of comfort, exploration and foraging behaviours by the chickens (EFSA, 2023); increasing NH₃ concentrations which can lead to birds' eyes lesions, respiratory issues, and severe pathological damage or infections (Miles et al., 2004; David et al., 2015; Cohuo-Colli et al., 2018). The assessment of litter quality can be done through various instrumental methods requiring time for analyses and/or specific costly equipment. In contrast, visual assessment can be conducted without any instruments, is instantaneous, and easily feasible. However, visual scoring may be considered subjective, this is why EURCAW-Poultry-SFA studied the validity, inter assessor reliability and intra-assessor repeatability of three visual scores (Mocz et al. 2024) from two scoring systems:

- the **Welfare Quality** Protocol© - one scoring scale (2009)
- the **Classyfarm** protocol - two complementary scoring scales: Friability and Humidity scores (IZSLER, 2023)

The study has shown that the three scores of both scoring systems were best suited for assessing litter when its moisture level is above 35% with better results in validity, reliability and

repeatability than when moisture level is below 35%. The three scores exhibited similar validity which was evaluated by comparing the visual scores with measurable moisture levels (see Figure 1 showing the results for moisture levels above 35%).

Figure 1. Scatter plot and correlations between Classyfarm scoring scales (A), and Welfare Quality scoring scale (B), and litter moisture when the litter moisture is above 35%. Classyfarm ranges from 1 to 10, 10 being very dry litter; Welfare Quality scoring ranges from 0 to 4, 0 being very dry litter.

Litter quality visual assessment in broiler sheds

However, the Classyfarm Friability score was the most reliable scoring scale regardless of litter moisture. Regarding intra-assessor repeatability, the Classyfarm Friability and Welfare Quality scores outperformed the Classyfarm Humidity score.

The Classyfarm protocol for litter assessment was intended to use both friability and humidity scores. Simplifying the litter assessment in the Classyfarm Protocol by retaining only the friability score may be advisable, as it was more reliable and repeatable compared to the Classyfarm Humidity score. Furthermore, although the Welfare Quality score had similar validity and repeatability, it appeared to be less reliable than the Classyfarm Friability score. Therefore, it is recommended to prioritize the use of the Classyfarm Friability score, particularly when comparing scores from multiple assessor

Methods of assessment proposed

The method of assessment consists in evaluating litter quality in 1 m² of distinct areas of the barn using the scoring scale described in Table 1. To reflect variability in litter quality, the assessment should be done in various areas in the barn such as near drinkers and feeders, close to a wall or away from feeders and drinkers (Brink et al. 2022). In that respect, EURCAW Poultry-SFA proposed to do the evaluation of the litter quality in at least 4 locations: under/near the drinkers, under/near the feeders, close to a wall and in the middle of the shed. The scores of these locations could be considered

independently or could be averaged to result in a mean score for the barn.

Table 1. Description of the visual scores for friability of the Classyfarm protocol (IZSLER, 2023)

Score	Classyfarm Friability Score Description
1	Completely caked
2	80-90 % area caked
3	70-80 % area caked
4	60-70 % area caked
5	50-60 % area caked
6	40 % area caked
7	30 % area caked
8	10 % area caked
9	Friable litter, small caked areas
10	Friable litter, no caked areas

References

- Brink, M., G. P. J. Janssens, And E. Delezie. 2022. How Do Moisture Content, Friability, and Crust Development of Litter Influence Ammonia Concentrations in Broiler Production? *Livestock Science* 265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2022.105109>
- Cohuo-Colli, J. M., Salinas-Ruíz, J., Hernández-Cázares, A. S., Hidalgo-Contreras, J. V., Brito-Damián, V. H., & Velasco-Velasco, J. (2018). Effect of litter density and foot health program on ammonia emissions in broiler chickens. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 27(2), 198-205. <https://doi:10.3382/japr/pfx058>
- Collett, S. R. (2012). Nutrition and wet litter problems in poultry. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, 173, 65-75.
- David, B., Mejdell, C., Michel, V., Lund, V., & Moe, R. O. (2015). Air quality in alternative housing systems may have an impact on laying hen welfare. Part II-ammonia. *Animals*, 5(3), 886-896. <https://doi:10.3390/ani5030389>
- EFSA (2023). Scientific Opinion on the welfare of broilers on farm. *EFSA Journal*, 21(2), 236. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7788>
- IZSLER (2023). Linee Guida Per La Categorizzazione Del Rischio Nell'Allevamento Del Pollo Da Carne.
- Miles, D. M., Branton, S. L., & Lott, B. D. (2004). Atmospheric ammonia is detrimental to the performance of modern commercial broilers. *Poultry Science*, 83(10), 1650-1654. <https://doi:10.1093/ps/83.10.1650>
- Mocz, F., Contreras-Jodar, A., Michel, V., & Guinebretière, M. (2024). Scientific study on the validity, reliability and repeatability of two visual scoring methods of assessment of the litter quality. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13889643>
- Shepherd, E. M., & Fairchild, B. D. (2010). Footpad dermatitis in poultry. *Poult Sci*, 89(10), 2043-2051. <https://doi:10.3382/ps.2010-00770>
- Shepherd, E. M., Fairchild, B. D., & Ritz, C. W. (2017). Alternative bedding materials and litter depth impact litter moisture and footpad dermatitis. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 26(4), 518-528. <https://doi:10.3382/japr/pfx024>
- Welfare Quality®. (2009). Welfare Quality® assessment protocol for poultry (broilers, laying hens). In Welfare Quality® Consortium, Lelystad, Netherlands.

Co-funded by
the European Union

AARHUS UNIVERSITY

IZSLER